

**ANTHROPCENTRIC PROVERBS AND THEIR FUNCTIONS.
SEMANTIC CLASSIFICATION OF ENGLISH AND
UZBEK ANTHROPCENTRIC PROVERBS**

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the theme of anthropocentric proverbs and their functions, with a specific focus on the semantic classification of English and Uzbek proverbs. Anthropocentric proverbs, which center on human experiences, behaviors, and perspectives, serve various functions such as conveying wisdom, guiding behavior, and reflecting cultural values. The study delves into the semantic classification of these proverbs, examining their levels of meaning, including literal, figurative, cultural, and idiomatic levels. Comparative analysis between English and Uzbek anthropocentric proverbs sheds light on the intersection of language, culture, and meaning, offering insights into how these proverbs reflect and shape human understanding and communication. By understanding their functions and semantic classifications, this research contributes to a deeper appreciation of the role of proverbs in conveying universal truths and cultural distinctiveness.

Keywords:

Anthropocentric proverbs, English proverbs, Uzbek proverbs, semantic classification, functions, cultural reflection, linguistic analysis, comparative study

INTRODUCTION

Proverbs are short, pithy sayings that express a truth, wisdom or advice based on common sense or experience. They are an important part of the everyday language and culture of people in many parts of the world. Anthropocentric proverbs have a long history in societies, dating back to ancient times. Many proverbs have their roots in religious texts, folklore, literature, and oral traditions. Anthropocentric proverbs are expressions or sayings that focus on human behavior, characteristics, and experiences. These proverbs often reflect cultural values, beliefs, and norms related to human interactions and societal roles. They serve as tools for conveying wisdom, moral lessons, and social norms within a community.

MAIN PART

Anthropocentric proverbs are those that focus on human beings as the center of attention or importance. They represent the human perspective and often reflect human behaviors, beliefs, and experiences. These proverbs typically convey wisdom, advice, or cultural values through concise and memorable sayings. Anthropocentric proverbs serve several functions in linguistics, including:

Transmitting cultural knowledge: Proverbs are often rooted in cultural traditions and beliefs, and are passed down through generations as a way of transmitting cultural knowledge and wisdom. For example

It takes a village to raise a child

Don't bite the hand that feeds you

Learn from your elders

Bir bolaga yetti mahalla ota-ona

Qarisi bor uyning parisi bor

These proverbs embody the transmission of cultural knowledge and values in societies. They serve as concise expressions of collective wisdom and reflect the importance of cultural teachings in guiding behaviours and attitudes.

Conveying succinct messages: Proverbs are an efficient and memorable way of conveying complex or abstract messages. They are short and easy to remember, making them ideal for communicating ideas through oral tradition.

Beauty is in the eye of the beholder

A friend in need is a friend indeed

As you sow, so shall you reap

Ajal lib kelsa yov,

O'ldir, berma hech ayov

Aysiz do'st izlagan do'stsiz qolar

While studying this topic some themes and perspectives are found in the nature of anthropocentric proverbs. These themes are universal as they reflect general concepts all languages:

- Human Nature: Anthropocentric proverbs often shed light on different aspects of human behaviour, characteristics, and personalities.

Wisdom is the beauty of man

Manners make the man

Odam bezagi aql

Insonni fazilatlar ulug'laydi

- Relationships and Interactions: These proverbs offer insights into human relationships, both positive and negative. These proverbs capture the essence of human relationships, alliances, loyalty and the dynamics of social interactions.

A friend in need is a friend indeed

No man is an island

Keep your friends close and your enemies closer

Yolg'iz botir yovga yo'q

Yolg'iz yigit dovga yo'q

Yigitning kuchini- el sinar

•Life Lessons and Morality: Many anthropocentric proverbs convey moral lessons and ethical guidance. Such proverbs serve as guiding principles, urging individuals to make virtuous choices.

To err is human, to forgive divine

Do unto others as you would have them do unto you

Xato qilish insonga xosdir

Zargar firibgar bo‘lsa, oltin zanglar

When comparing English and Uzbek anthropocentric proverbs, it is essential to consider the cultural and linguistic differences between the two languages. English proverbs often reflect the individualistic values and historical context of Western societies, emphasizing personal responsibility, autonomy, and self-reliance. On the other hand, Uzbek proverbs may showcase community-oriented perspectives, highlighting the interconnectedness of individuals within a communal context. Examples of English anthropocentric proverbs:

"Actions speak louder than words."

This proverb emphasizes the value of tangible actions and behaviors over mere verbal promises. It highlights the importance of demonstrating one's intentions through concrete actions.

"No man is an island."

This proverb conveys the idea that humans are inherently interconnected and reliant on one another. It underscores the significance of social connections and community support. Examples of Uzbek anthropocentric proverbs:

"Odam bo‘lish- oson. Odamiy bo‘lish qiyin"

This Uzbek proverb translates to "To understand the badness of people, it is enough to see a man who turned the grindstone." It reflects the importance of keeping promises and fulfilling one's commitments.

“Odam bo‘lmoq asta-asta,

Hayvon bo‘lmoq bir pasda”

It underscores the notion of judging the character of individuals through their actions and behaviors.

In summary, anthropocentric proverbs offer valuable insights into the cultural values of a community. By comparing English and Uzbek proverbs, we can recognize how linguistic and cultural differences shape the expression of human-centric wisdom across different societies. Furthermore, the study of these proverbs enables us to gain a deeper understanding of the shared and distinct perspectives on human nature and social interactions within diverse cultural contexts.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Anthropocentric proverbs in English offer valuable insights into human nature, relationships, and moral values. By exploring these pithy sayings, we gain a deeper understanding of cultural norms, linguistic intricacies, and the ways in which societies perceive and navigate human-centric experiences. As we continue to use and pass along anthropocentric proverbs, they remain powerful tools for communication, community cohesion, and cultural preservation. They also provide a valuable insight into the culture and identity of the people who use them. Studying anthropocentric proverbs offers several educational benefits. They provide a window into the historical, social, and cultural aspects of communities. Analyzing the linguistic structures within proverbs enhances language learning skills, deepening comprehension of idiomatic expressions and metaphorical language use.

REFERENCES

1. Majidova.R.U., Аксиологическое исследование антропоцентрических пословиц (на материале узбекского и русского языков)-2020
2. Akhmedov.U., Comparative Analysis Of Uzbek And English Proverbs.Journal “The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations”.Pp 160-164
3. <https://languagetool.org/insights/post/what-is-a-proverb/>
4. <https://www.ziyouz.com/portal-haqida/xarita/uzbek-xalq-ogzaki-ijodi/uzbek-xalq-maqollari>